

Linked Open Data and Hellenistic Numismatics

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The American Numismatic Society (ANS), founded in 1858, is a leading research institute for the discipline, with a large collection objects, an archive pertaining to the Society that also contains primary research materials from prominent scholars, and the world's largest specialist library for numismatics. The collection of coins, medals, and other related monetary instruments is among the largest in the world, and nearly 600,000 records are available online through its Open Access web portal, MANTIS (<http://numismatics.org/search>). The Society's collection spans all periods and cultures, but its holdings are particularly strong in the area of Greek numismatics, for which there are nearly 100,000 objects – half of which (as of the publication of this article) – have been photographed and made available in the public domain.

Among these Greek coins, nearly 11,000 depict Alexander the Great, produced either under his authority during his lifetime or as posthumous issues for which Alexander is the stated authority. This paper will focus on these coins and their integration into the broader scholarly ecosystem for Hellenistic numismatics (including archival and library materials) through the implementation of technical Linked Open Data (LOD) methodologies.

CURRENT LIMITATIONS WITH DISPARATE DATABASE SYSTEMS

Many museums or archaeological excavations maintain databases for their collections. Since the advent of the World Wide Web, many such organisations have made their databases available to the public. The ANS database evolved from a DOS-based platform in the 1980s into a FileMaker Pro database, which still serves as the primary data entry point for curatorial staff. Part of this collection was published online into a MySQL database in the early 2000s followed by a significant overhaul in web-based information architecture in 2011 with the deployment of Numishare (<https://github.com/ewg118/numishare>), an open source numismatic collection publication framework initially developed at the University of Virginia Library. Dubbed MANTIS upon its release in spring 2011, the ANS collection has seen continuous development and evolution in the seven years since its launch: general user interface improvements, more thorough integration of standardised vocabulary identifiers, new geographic or quantitative analysis features, and further compliance to open web standards, such as LOD, including the implementation of the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF: <http://iiif.io/>).

While the ANS collection of Greek coins is among the largest, the cabinets of the Münzkabinett of the Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, the British Museum in London, the

Bibliothèque nationale de France (BnF) in Paris, and the Kunsthistorisches Museum in Vienna, and others are equally important for research. Prior to the advent of the Internet, a scholar would travel in person to each of these collections to conduct research. The Web has made this much easier, but, until recent advancements described later in this paper, he or she still needed to visit each of the online collections to gather research data. There are various problems with this methodology. Firstly, online databases may represent an incomplete cross-section of a collection. The coins of Vienna had been catalogued in several databases (most recently Microsoft Access), but have only been available to the public since 2014 through an adaptation of the Berlin Münzkabinett framework. The BnF only recently began a programme to photograph their Greek collection, which has been made available through the generalised interface for all Special Collections materials (manuscripts, photographs, historic monographs, etc.) published by the library through its web portal, Gallica (<http://gallica.bnf.fr/>). At the ANS, while half of the Greek collection has been photographed, the coverage across all departments is only about one-quarter. The incompleteness of digitisation across these five large collections paints only a partial picture of Hellenistic history, art, and economics, and the collections of smaller civic and university museums tend to slip through the cracks. The Fralin Museum at the University of Virginia contains only two Alexanders, and it is doubtful any numismatist would ever travel to view them in person or even think to look for the collection online.

Beyond shortcomings with respect to physical or online access, language is another barrier. When searching disparate databases, one must wrangle different interfaces in different languages, and even data are typically only available in the language of the publishing institution. When searching the ANS or British Museum databases, one must know to search for “tetradrachm” (or “4 drachm” due to inconsistencies in data entry), “tétradrachme” in a French database, or “tetradrachme”, in a German one to yield successful queries for the Greek denomination. Regardless of language, scholars of Greek numismatics will agree these are three spellings for the same intellectual concept. It is for this reason that Andrew Meadows and Sebastian Heath, then of the ANS, founded Nomisma.org: to define the concepts of numismatics according to Semantic Web and Linked Open Data principles.

LINKED OPEN NUMISMATIC DATA

Nomisma.org: Things Not Strings

Established in 2010, the Nomisma.org project is an international collaborative effort to define numismatic concepts according to Linked Open Data methodologies. Rather than relying on textual strings to define controlled vocabulary, in which terminology varies based on language, concepts are defined by Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) which are accessible on the web through the HTTP protocol. These principles were outlined by Tim Berners-Lee¹, and can be summarized as follows: when a URI is dereferenced by HTTP, either by a browser or by an automated process, that both human- (HTML) and machine-readable

¹ Berners-Lee 2006.

data are delivered. These machine-readable data are in the form of Resource Description Framework (RDF), a technical expression of the linkage between documents or entities – essentially, a network graph following ontologies and models published by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and other organisations².

In simpler terms, the concept of a tetradrachm is therefore defined by <http://nomisma.org/id/tetradrachm>. If one were to visit this URI in a browser, one would find basic information about the denomination: labels in different languages, URIs to the same concept defined in other LOD controlled vocabulary systems (such as the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus, Wikidata.org, and the British Museum thesaurus). Multilingual labels are among the most important features of Nomisma. While English, German, and French scholars agree that <http://nomisma.org/id/tetradrachm> is a stable identifier for the concept of the denomination, the preferred label for the concept can still be represented in any language, which therefore facilitates web interfaces in multiple languages. Similarly, by linking Nomisma-defined concepts with URIs in other systems, Nomisma serves as a bridge between different datasets and enables further interoperability. This can be seen especially with geographic concepts such as mints and regions. The Greek mint of Amphipolis (<http://nomisma.org/id/amphipolis>; fig. 1) is linked to the same concept in the Pleiades Gazetteer of Ancient Places (<http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/501347>), which makes it possible for Nomisma partners to integrate their ancient coins into the Pelagios Project, a broad aggregation of content (epigraphy, coins, archaeological photographs, literary resources, and others) related to ancient geography.

Note the following data represented as RDF in the Turtle serialisation:

```
<http://nomisma.org/id/amphipolis> rdf:type nmo:Mint;
  skos:prefLabel "Amphipolis"@en, "Амфиполис"@ru;
  skos:closeMatch <http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/501347>;
  skos:broader <http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian\_and\_bottiaean\_district>
  geo:location ?loc.
?loc rdf:type geo:SpatialThing;
  geo:lat "40.823597";
  geo:long "23.846565"
```

Broken down into individual statements about the concept of “Amphipolis”, each statement grammatically consists of three parts: subject, predicate (also called a property), and object. It is essentially a computational syntax that represents how humans structure knowledge. “Amphipolis”, represented by the URI has a preferred label (skos:prefLabel in the Simple Knowledge Organization System [SKOS] ontology)³, has a parent concept of the “Strymonian and Bottiaean District” (derived from Barclay Head’s *Historia Numorum*), and is a close match (skos:closeMatch) to the related URI in the Pleiades Gazetteer of Ancient Places. Lastly, “Amphipolis” is the concept of a mint (nmo:Mint in the Nomisma.org ontology)

² More technical overviews about Nomisma.org have been published over the years. See Gruber 2012, Gruber 2013, Meadows and Gruber 2013.

³ SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System, published by the World Wide Web Consortium. Available at <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>

amphipolis (nmo:Mint)

skos:prefLabel

[Amphipolis \(ar\)](#), [Amphironic \(bg\)](#), [Amphipolis \(br\)](#), [Amphipolis \(ca\)](#), [Amphipol \(cs\)](#), [Amphipolis \(de\)](#), [Αμφίπολη \(el\)](#), [Amphipolis \(en\)](#), [Amphipolis \(es\)](#), [المفطيسية \(fa\)](#), [Amphipolis \(fi\)](#), [Amphipolis \(fr\)](#), [Amphipoli \(it\)](#), [آمفیپولیس \(ja\)](#), [Amphipolis \(ka\)](#), [Amphipolis \(nl\)](#), [Amphipoli \(nn\)](#), [Amphipolis \(pl\)](#), [Amphipolis \(pt\)](#), [Amphipolis \(ro\)](#), [Amphironic \(ru\)](#), [Amphipolis \(sr\)](#), [Amphironic \(sr\)](#), [Amphipolis \(sv\)](#), [Amphipolis \(tr\)](#), [Amphironic \(uk\)](#), [Amphipol \(vi\)](#), [Amphipolis \(vo\)](#)
 The mint at the ancient site of Amphipolis in Macedonia. (en)

dterms:isParOf <http://nomisma.org/id/greek-numismatics>

geo:location <http://nomisma.org/id/amphipolis#this>

rdfs:type [skos:Concept](http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian-and-bottiaean-district)

[skos:broader](http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian-and-bottiaean-district) <http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian-and-bottiaean-district>

[skos:closeMatch](http://collection.britishmuseum.org/id/PLACE%32013) <http://collection.britishmuseum.org/id/PLACE%32013>

[skos:closeMatch](http://dpepda.org/resource/Amphipolis) <http://dpepda.org/resource/Amphipolis>

[skos:closeMatch](http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/5011347) <http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/5011347>

[skos:closeMatch](http://viaf.org/viaf/240924264) <http://viaf.org/viaf/240924264>

[skos:closeMatch](http://vocab.getty.edu/ign/7011094) <http://vocab.getty.edu/ign/7011094>

[skos:closeMatch](http://www.geonames.org/7368993) <http://www.geonames.org/7368993>

[skos:closeMatch](https://www.freebase.com/m/051q) <https://www.freebase.com/m/051q>

[skos:closeMatch](https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q217414) <https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q217414>

#this (geo:SpatialThing)

dterms:isParOf http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian_and_bottiaean_district#this

geo:lat [40.823597](http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian_and_bottiaean_district#this)

geo:long [23.846565](http://nomisma.org/id/strymonian_and_bottiaean_district#this)

Associated Types (max 10) ▼

[+ View SPARQL for full query](#)

[📄 Download CSV](#)

Type

Price 153

Mint Amphipolis

Denomination Drachma

Date 336 B.C. - 323 B.C.

Type Series

Price (1991)

Example

Price 154

Mint Amphipolis

Denomination Hemidrachm

Date 336 B.C. - 323 B.C.

Price (1991)

Price 155

Mint Amphipolis

Denomination Diobol

Date 336 B.C. - 323 B.C.

Price (1991)

Export

Linked Data [GitHub File](#) [RDF/XML](#) [RDF/TTL](#) [JSON-LD](#)

Geographic Data [KML](#) [geo:JSON \(mints\)](#) [geo:JSON \(hoards\)](#) [geo:JSON \(finds\)](#)

Fig. 1. HTML rendition of the URI <http://nomisma.org/id/amphipolis>

with a spatial component, represented by latitude and longitude. Each of these three-part statements is called a “triple”, and a database for storing triples is a “triplestore.”

The HTML rendition of Nomisma URIs often includes further research context: maps showing the geographic distribution of a given concept (*e.g.* the mints that produced tetradrachms), examples of coin types related to the concept, and basic metrical or distribution analyses rendered in charts in the *d3js* Javascript library. Machine-readable data are available in every major serialisation of RDF (XML, Turtle, JSON-LD), and geographic data are available in the open standard, GeoJSON.

Today, more than 6,000 URIs have been designated by Nomisma.org, across many different categories: object types, materials, denominations, people, political entities, mints, regions, types of coin wear, fields of numismatics, etc... These concepts are published into a triplestore, and are available for query, either by humans or machine processes through an endpoint conforming to the W₃C SPARQL protocol (<https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>). This SPARQL endpoint is an integral application in the overall software architecture of Nomisma.org; it integrates data about physical coins, coin types, and hoards, making large-scale aggregation of numismatic data possible. Nomisma’s SPARQL endpoint averages more than 100,000 queries per day, predominately executed by other machine processes, including other ANS digital projects. Nomisma.org is among the most heavily used LOD information systems in the cultural heritage sector, and has recently been cited by the ARIADNE as a “leading example” among archaeologically-oriented LOD projects⁴.

PELLA: Linked Open Data for Greek Coin Type Corpora

In 2012, Numishare was extended beyond its initial design as a framework for collections of physical objects to accommodate the publication of coin types. This enhancement was made for Online Coins of the Roman Empire (OCRE: <http://numismatics.org/ocre>), a collaboration between the ANS and the Institute for the Study of the Ancient World at New York University. Concluding in 2017 after three years of funding from the U.S. National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), OCRE has published all coin types from the Roman Empire, spanning 500 years from Augustus to Zeno (31 B.C. to A.D. 491). Subsequent online type corpora have been published in Numishare by the ANS: Coinage of the Roman Republic Online (<http://numismatics.org/crro>), PELLA (the coinage of Macedonian kings: <http://numismatics.org/pella>), and, most recently, Seleucid Coins Online (<http://numismatics.org/sco>), which is the second typological entry into the NEH-funded Hellenistic Royal Coinages (HRC) project.

These online corpora follow the same principles established by Nomisma.org. Like mints, denominations, or rulers, coin types are also fundamentally intellectual concepts, albeit more complex ones – a conceptual typology composed of other concepts. Historically, coin types are uniquely numbered, thematically organised, and published in volumes of printed books. Printed volumes often contain photographic plates to show examples of physical specimens of each type from major collections, but space is always limited in monographs,

and it is therefore impossible to show every possible example within a reference work. Over time, these printed volumes become the standard reference work for a category of coins, and curators and scholars will insert these type numbers into museum or archaeological databases. The particular format of the reference is not uniform in all databases, making search difficult across multiple systems.

Online corpora are a technical evolution of traditional organisational methods. The PELLA project is a catalogue of coin types, in its initial phase, based on the numbering system devised by Martin Price in *The Coinage in the Name of Alexander the Great and Philip Arrhidaeus* (1991). Each of the more than 4,500 types defined in Price's catalogue have been assigned a URI in PELLA. "Price 6" is represented by <http://numismatics.org/pella/id/price.6> (fig. 2). The machine-readable data underlying this URI indicate that the type is a `TypeSeriesItem` in the `Nomisma.org` ontology, and this record includes various properties from several other ontologies to comprise the title, mint, denomination, obverse and reverse legends and type descriptions (in English, French, and German), monograms, symbols, or deities depicted on the obverse and reverse, the authority responsible for issue, as well the date range under which the type was produced.

The HTML page for human consumption includes these typological data, as well as a map showing the mint and geographic distribution of finds and hoards, a list of example specimens across many different museum and archaeological datasets (including, in most cases, photographs), and the average axis, diameter, and weight of the type. There are additional interfaces for distribution and metrical analysis.

Price 6 is a silver tetradrachm issued by Alexander the Great at Amphipolis, and each of these concepts links to the relevant `Nomisma` URI in the underlying RDF. Since the `Nomisma` LOD include labels in other languages, the interface for PELLA is fully translated into French and German (as well as being available in English), and is at least partially available in nearly 20 other languages, including Arabic (owing to translations of the `Numishare` interface and `Nomisma` IDs in `OCRE`). Each of the individual attributes of coin type (mint, authority, etc.) is indexed into `Apache Solr`, the search engine that underlies the `Numishare` framework, enabling textual search of type descriptions, legends, or keywords anywhere within the record metadata, as well as faceted search for typological attributes in an intuitive user interface (e.g. <http://numismatics.org/pella/results>)⁵.

The `Linked Open Data` for PELLA, as well as the other online type corpora, are published into the `Nomisma.org` SPARQL endpoint. Physical specimens from the larger institutions such as the ANS, BnF, British Museum, and Berlin are mapped into RDF conforming to the `Nomisma` ontology and data model and also ingested into the SPARQL endpoint⁶. These specimens include URIs for the coin type, expressed by the `hasTypeSeriesItem` property in

5 For a more detailed explanation of `Numishare`'s underlying software architecture, see Gruber 2013 and Gruber 2016.

6 See <http://nomisma.org/documentation/contribute> for more details on the `Nomisma` model for contributing data about physical specimens to `Nomisma`.

Typological Description

Object Type: Coin
Manufacture: Struck
Material: Silver
Denomination: Tetradrachm

Date Range

From Date: 336 B.C.
To Date: 323 B.C.

Authority

Authority: Alexander III of Macedon
Stated Authority: Alexander III of Macedon

Geographic

Mint: Amphipolis (uncertain)
Region: Europe–Macedon–Strymonian and Bottiaean District

Obverse

Type: Head of beardless Heracles right wearing lion skin headress
Deity: Heracles

Reverse

Type: Zeus seated on stool-throne left, eagle on outstretched right hand, sceptre in left hand
Deity: Zeus
Legend: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ
Symbol: janiform-head vase (Left Field)

References

Reference:

Map

Year	Mint	Findspot
335BC		
334BC		
333BC		
332BC		
331BC		
330BC		
329BC		
328BC		
327BC		
326BC		
325BC		
324BC		
323BC		
322BC		
321BC		
320BC		
319BC		
318BC		
317BC		
316BC		
315BC		
314BC		
313BC		
312BC		
311BC		
310BC		
309BC		
308BC		
307BC		
306BC		
305BC		
304BC		
303BC		
302BC		
301BC		
300BC		

Legend

View map in fullscreen.

Examples of this type

Silver Tetradrachm of Alexander III of Macedon, Amphipolis, 336 B.C. - 323 B.C., 1944.100.26720

Collection American Numismatic Society
Axis 5
Weight 17.14

Silver Tetradrachm of Alexander III of Macedon, Amphipolis, 336 B.C. - 323 B.C., 1944.100.26719

Collection American Numismatic Society
Axis 5
Weight 17.08

Fig. 2. HTML rendition of the URI: <http://numismatics.org/pella/id/price.6>

the Nomisma ontology. Further properties are employed for capturing measurements, links to digital images, and, as of early 2017, IIF web service metadata⁷.

An increasing number of Nomisma collaborators are publishing their images online according to the IIF specification, beginning with Rutgers University Library. The ANS published more than 320,000 photographs through IIF for 160,000 objects, 55,000 of which are accessible through online type corpora such as PELLA. The Fralin Museum collection published by the University of Virginia Library is the most recent partner to migrate to IIF in December 2017. The integration of IIF images into Nomisma.org not only enables zooming of high resolution images directly within the PELLA user interface itself, but also facilitates the dynamic generation of IIF manifests (a container for one or more images and associated metadata) by means of SPARQL query results serialised into JSON-LD conforming to the manifest specification. The IIF manifest for Price 6 (<http://numismatics.org/pella/manifest/price.6>) includes every applicable image from every coin linked to the Price 6 URI. It is in this type of interface that symbols, monograms, or iconographic motifs may be annotated with their associated URIs, following the W3C's Web Annotation specification⁸. We have yet to implement image annotation within our own Linked Open Data infrastructure, but it will function by the conclusion of the HRC project (2020).

There are nearly 200,000 physical specimens connected to published coin type URIs incorporated into the Nomisma SPARQL endpoint. More than half are Roman Imperial coins linked to OCRE, but about 20,000 Alexanders from 13 institutions are available through PELLA, ranging from 1 at Düsseldorf to 10,818 at the ANS. The major collections in New York, Paris, London, Berlin, and Vienna are represented, but where PELLA separates itself from printed corpora or collection-specific sylloges is the inclusion of small civic or university museums (as well as excavation data from Priene) that neither have large enough collections to necessitate a printed sylloge nor would ever be included in the photographic plates for a type corpus. But these smaller contributors, with their own measurement data, photographs, and, potentially, findspot information (geographic location in addition to burial date) help to fill in gaps in existing scholarship and paint a more complete picture of the circulation of Greek coinage.

Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards Online

An Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards (IGCH) is a monograph published in 1973 by the American Numismatic Society on behalf of the International Numismatic Commission, that catalogued more than 2,400 Greek coin hoards. Building on earlier works published by the ANS, such as Sydney Noe's *A Bibliography of Greek Coin Hoards* (1937), and in combination with other archival records held in the Society and elsewhere, *IGCH* was the most complete account of hoards available at the time.

As part of the Nomisma.org pilot, Heath and Meadows generated URIs for all *IGCH* hoards within the Nomisma.org namespace. The Demanhur hoard (*IGCH* 1664) was therefore

⁷ Charles 2017.

⁸ Sanderson *et al.* 2017.

identified by <http://nomisma.org/id/igch1664> (which has subsequently migrated to a new domain: <http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664>). At this phase, *IGCH* entries on coinhoards.org include verbatim transcriptions of the descriptions of the hoard, extracted directly from the printed volume. These transcriptions are encoded into XHTML and given semantic RDFa tagging for the geographic findspot, burial date, and the mints associated with the hoard. The XHTML are distilled into RDF following the Nomisma ontology. Much work remains to be done to convert *IGCH* Online into a more robust and dynamic research dataset, especially with regard to encoding the precise numerical count of coins attributed to mints, authorities, and specific or general typological references. Presently, the findspot coordinates and index of mints enable the visualisation of the geographic distribution within a hoard.

Insofar as individual specimens are concerned, the ANS and several other Nomisma partners (such as Berlin) have incorporated *IGCH* URIs into their object databases. Upon export into the Nomisma model, the hoard URI is mapped to the Dublin Core Terms `isPartOf` property (`dcterms:isPartOf`). The RDF representation of the linkage between object, type, and hoard is summarised as follows:

```
<http://numismatics.org/collection/1944.100.26728> rdf:type nmo:NumismaticObject;
  nmo:hasTypeSeriesItem <http://numismatics.org/pella/id/price.6>;
  dcterms:isPartOf <http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664> .
<http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664> rdf:type nmo:Hoard;
  nmo:hasClosingDate "-0318";
  nmo:hasFindspot <http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664#findspot> .
<http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664#findspot> rdf:type geo:SpatialThing;
  geo:lat "30.4619444444";
  geo:long "31.1694444444"
```

The Turtle syntax above is an RDF representation of logical statements about an entity. The coin [1944.100.26728](http://numismatics.org/collection/1944.100.26728) (<http://numismatics.org/collection/1944.100.26728>) in the ANS collection is designated as a “Numismatic Object” in the Nomisma ontology. It is an item belonging to the type of Price 6 and is part of the hoard *IGCH* 1664. The burial date is 318 B.C. and it was found at a particular latitude and longitude.

There is much that can be inferred about the data above. First, Price 6 was likely struck in Amphipolis as late as 323 B.C.. In Nomisma.org, Amphipolis (<http://nomisma.org/id/amphipolis>), also bears geographic coordinates. Therefore, in MANTIS, we are able to generate a map for [1944.100.26728](http://numismatics.org/collection/1944.100.26728) that shows the places of its production and burial. A more complicated SPARQL query can be executed for aggregating all hoards of all coins associated with Price 6. The map and timeline are visible in the landing pages for individual types in PELLA. The following query will extract the coordinates for all coin hoards associated with Price 6:

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?hoard ?lat ?long WHERE {
  ?coin nmo:hasTypeSeriesItem <http://numismatics.org/pella/id/price.6>;
  dcterms:isPartOf ?hoard .
  ?hoard nmo:hasFindspot ?findspot .
  ?findspot geo:lat ?lat ;
  geo:long ?long }
```


Fig. 3. Map generated by Nomisma.org of coin hoards associated in Pella with Price 6.

When executed through the Nomisma.org web-based SPARQL interface, a map will automatically be generated showing four coin hoards, three of which were found in Egypt (fig. 3).

Turning our attention to the individual characteristics of Price 6, we are then able to infer increasingly complex queries that enable us to visualize the geographic distribution of tetradrachms (both the mints that produced them and their circulation throughout the ancient world), the types of Alexander the Great in general, and the circulation of coinage produced in Amphipolis.

The map in fig. 4 depicts the distribution of tetradrachms, with the mints represented by blue dots and the hoards by red⁹. The map, however, is incomplete. It is only a representation of those coins at the American Numismatic Society and Berlin that are connected to typologies published by PELLA and Seleucid Coins Online that also have been catalogued with *IGCH* URIs. The more data aggregated into this system the more comprehensive the map will become. We are only glimpsing the full potential of Linked Open Data applied to Greek numismatics.

ENHANCING CONTEXT THROUGH ARCHIVES AND LIBRARIES

In addition to its large specialist library, the ANS has published a journal and monographs for over a century, and it maintains an archive of unique research materials authored by prominent scholars who were officers or members of the Society. Since 2012, it has been a primary goal of ANS digital projects to enhance the research value of its online collection

9 The map and underlying geographic data (in GeoJSON) are available at <http://nomisma.org/id/tetradrachm>

Fig. 4. Map of mints and hoard findspots for all tetradrachms recorded at Nomisma.org.

and research databases (including IGCH and PELLA) by providing access to these archival materials. In 2016, the ANS was awarded funding from the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Mellon Foundation as part of the Humanities Open Book Program to digitise and make available about 85 out-of-print monographs of interest and value to the numismatic community. A second phase is currently underway, and by mid-2018, the total number of Open Access monographs published through the ANS Digital Library (<http://numismatics.org/digitalibrary>) will grow to approximately 200. These archival and library materials are now integrated into other ANS information systems, from MANTIS to IGCH. The technical specifics about this architecture have been detailed in Gruber 2016, but a synopsis will be provided below.

Archer: the ANS Archives

Launched in November 2011, Archer (the ANS's archival platform) provided the public with the Society's archival records. At first comprising only finding aids, Archer has grown to include photographs and, in June 2014, saw the publication of the first of Edward T. Newell's Greek numismatic research notebooks. Each of these genres of materials follow established library and archival standards: the finding aids are tagged in an XML schema, Encoded Archival Description (EAD), metadata about photographs are captured in Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS), and the notebooks are encoded as a list of facsimile images in a Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) XML document¹⁰. All three metadata schemas are published in the open source framework, EADitor (<https://github.com/ewgu8/eaditor>), which was

10 The technical details of the image annotation and TEI integration of Newell's notebooks are available at <http://eaditor.blogspot.com/2014/06/first-newell-notebook-published-in.html>

initially developed by Gruber at the University of Virginia Library starting in 2009 before seeing continuous enhancement at the ANS.

The most recent major advancement in EADitor was its support of IIIF for digital images. Alongside the publication of the ANS numismatic collection images into the IIIF specification came the deployment of IIIF for the ANS' archival photographs and digitised notebooks of Newell, in addition to revision of rights statements placing all pre-1923 photographs into the public domain¹¹. Among the most interesting collections in the ANS is the Papers of Agnes Baldwin Brett (<http://numismatics.org/archives/ark:/53695/nnan0037>), who was a prominent numismatist and curator at the Society from 1909-1912. This collection features high-resolution photographs of Brett's travels through Italy, Greece, and Turkey in the early 20th century. Many of these photographs depict other notable scholars or ancient monuments, which have been annotated with relevant URIs in the Virtual International Authority File (VIAF: <https://viaf.org>) or the Pleiades Gazetteer of Ancient Places, respectively. By means of mapping EAD into RDF conforming to the Pelagios data model, these archival photographs have been integrated into the Pelagios Commons' Peripleo framework (<http://peripleo.pelagios.org/>) and are available to a broader audience interested in the ancient world.

The research notebooks of Edward T. Newell are of particular interest with respect to Hellenistic numismatics. Newell was one of the leading scholars of Greek coinage in his day and served as President of the Society. Dozens of his personal research notebooks are housed in the ANS archives, until recently accessible only to those scholars able to travel to New York to consult them. With a grant from the Gladys Kriebel Delmas Foundation, in 2014 the ANS digitised 43 notebooks. With the aid of Andrew Meadows, ANS Archivist David Hill, and Assistant Archivist Arnold Tescher used EADitor's back-end functionality to annotate roughly one-quarter of these notebooks, linking Newell's handwritten notes and symbols to URIs representing *IGCH* hoards, coins in MANTIS, bibliographic references in OCLC Worldcat, and other scholars identified in VIAF.

One such notebook from 1939 (<http://numismatics.org/archives/ark:/53695/nnan187715>; fig. 5) includes annotation of coins from Newell's personal collection that were found in *IGCH*1664 (referred to as "Demanhur"), later bequeathed to the ANS. Every annotation on every individual page is mapped into RDF following the Open Annotation standard¹². All related digital archival annotations are stored together with the RDF serialisations of the EAD, MODS, and TEI content in a separate SPARQL endpoint maintained by the ANS as part of the Archer framework, making it possible to link from a coin in MANTIS or hoard on coinhoards.org to the precise page in Newell's notebook where that coin or hoard had been mentioned.

- 11 For more information see "EADitor now supports EAD and MODS to IIIF manifest generation" (<http://eaditor.blogspot.com/2017/10/eaditor-now-supports-ead-and-mods-to.html>) and "Newell notebooks migrated to IIIF" (<http://eaditor.blogspot.com/2017/10/newell-notebooks-migrated-to-iiif.html>), both published in October 2017.
- 12 Sanderson, Ciccarese, and Van de Sompel 2013. Open Annotation has been superseded by Web Annotation (Sanderson 2017) and these annotations will be migrated into the new specification in the near future.

Edward T. Newell hoard notebook, circa 1939

Newell, Edward Theodore, 1886-1941

Publication Statement

Publisher American Numismatic Society
 Publication Place New York (N.Y.)
 Donum <http://numismatics.org/library/187715>

Abstract

Notebook of handwritten notes on ancient Greek coin hoards, including Aleppo, 1893; Afium Kara Hissar, Arpagot, 1918; Adrianople; Asia Minor, 1929; Babylon, 1900; Byblos, 1931; Chalcis, 1935; Chaicidice (Olynthus?); Demanthur, 1900; Epidaurus, 1903; Gebal (Byblos), 1931; Homs, 1934; Homs, 1927; Khoisabad; Mesopotamia (Dunne); Nicomedia (probably Thessalian hoard); Tell Halar, 1911; Thessalian, 1938. Also, one loose sheet of Pera Palace Hotel (Constantinople) letterhead containing four pages of notes labeled "Antioch" Hoard.

Index

- Aleppo (Syria)**
Appears on: 1
- Amphipolis**
Appears on: Loose 1
- Asia Minor**
Appears on: Loose 1
- Blanchard, Ralph Huntington, 1875-1936**
Appears on: 17
- Bronze Nummus, Alexandria, AD 295 - AD 296.**
1944.100.1227
Appears on: 19
- Cosson, Charles Alexander, baron de**
Appears on: 17
- Dow, Sterling, 1903-1995**
Appears on: 66
- Dunand, Maurice**
Appears on: 68
- Halil Edhem, 1861-1938**
Appears on: 1

Edward T. Newell hoard notebook, circa 1939

Fig. 5. Newell's hoard notebook, c. 1939.

The coin <http://numismatics.org/collection/1944.100.26728> is annotated on page 17 of this notebook, and a user visiting this web page in MANTIS is able to scroll down below the map and view a link to the notebook (and a link to page 17, which is also clickable), as well as any other relevant library or archival materials. Similarly, this notebook will appear under a list of annotations at the hoard URI, <http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664>. IGCH 1664 is mentioned numerous times in two of Newell's notebooks, as well as several out-of-print monographs published in the ANS Digital Library (<http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664#associated-content>).

The Digital Library

The first iteration of the American Numismatic Society Digital Library was released to the public to coincide with the International Numismatic Congress held in Taormina, Sicily in September, 2015. The Digital Library was initially designed as a means of providing access to numismatic electronic theses and dissertations. Architecturally similar to Numishare and EADitor, the underlying Digital Library framework was built on ETDPub (<https://github.com/AmericanNumismaticSociety/etdpub>), an open source application developed by Gruber. Shortly thereafter, the functionality of ETDPub was extended to support the publication of electronic monographs conforming to the TEI standard for text transcription in response to the ANS' successful bid as part of the NEH-Mellon Humanities Open Book Program.

As a publisher, the ANS has released nearly 500 monographs over its lifetime, nearly all of which have been distributed to university libraries across the globe. As part of the Google Books project, many of these monographs were scanned by Google's university partners and were later made available through the University of Michigan-sponsored HathiTrust Digital Library (<https://www.hathitrust.org/>). Since all of the Society's monographs were published in 1923 (the advent of modern U.S. copyright law) or after they were not publicly accessible. Director of Publications Andrew Reinhard submitted a revised license agreement with HathiTrust in early 2015, granting a Creative Commons Public Domain mark to these works. While research data-oriented projects (like PELLA and MANTIS) have had open licenses since their inception, Reinhard's decision to place these monographs into the Public Domain was the first step in a broader Open Access policy for ANS publications.

In late 2015, the ANS was awarded the Humanities Open Book Program grant, and about 85 PDFs of scanned books (predominantly from the *Numismatic Notes and Monographs*, *Numismatic Studies* series and *Coinage of the Americas Conference* proceedings) were sent to a vendor in India to be transcribed into TEI. These TEI files were returned to the ANS and further tagging was conducted by Gruber and Whitney Christopher, a Digital Humanities specialist from King's College London. Much like the Newell notebooks, particular focus was placed upon adding value to the ebooks by tagging relevant people, places, events, and subject topics, including links to coins in MANTIS, IGCH URIs, and references to coin types published in OCRE, CRRO, etc. These books and their links are readable on the web with a browser, but also downloadable as PDF and EPUB 3.0.1 files that can be viewed on any mobile device. These links from book to Nomisma-defined concepts, coins in the ANS collection, hoards, etc. transform the book from mere prose into a portal that provides further context about the entities described.

These links work both ways. The basic metadata and document structure of these ebooks are also represented as RDF and ingested into Archer's SPARQL endpoint. Each atomised logical section of a book is also identified by a URI, and relevant subjects within the section enable that section to be integrated as research context into the ANS' other platforms. For example, there is a chapter on the Demanhur hoard (*IGCH 1664*) in Margaret Thompson's *Alexander Drachm Mints I* (<http://numismatics.org/digitalibrary/ark:/53695/nnan49321>), and so users may access works in the Digital Library from IGCH URIs in the same fashion as Newell's notebooks.

The following SPARQL query will extract all annotations from archival resources and monographs published into the Archer triplestore:

```
SELECT ?target ?title ?bookTitle ?source ?abstract ?creator ?name ?thumbnail ?abstract
WHERE {
  ?s oa:hasBody <http://coinhoards.org/id/igch1664> ;
    oa:hasTarget ?target .
  ?target dcterms:source ?source ;
    dcterms:title ?title .
  ?source dcterms:title ?bookTitle ;
    dcterms:creator ?creator .
  OPTIONAL {?source foaf:thumbnail ?thumbnail}
  OPTIONAL {?source dcterms:abstract ?abstract}
  OPTIONAL {?creator foaf:name ?name}}
```

Effectively, this query obtains all annotations about *IGCH 1664* at the level in which they appear in Newell notebooks (by page) or ebooks in the ANS Digital Library (lowest-level section). The query will extract basic bibliographic metadata such as section title, book title, author, and cover-page thumbnail image, if available.

IGCH 1664 is among the most referenced coin hoards among Newell's notebooks and the American Numismatic Society's published monographs, but the coverage across all monographs indicates that more than 5% of *IGCH* hoards were mentioned at least once in the 85 books digitised in the first round of the Humanities Open Book Program. Some notable figures:

- 349 mentions of 164 different Greek coin hoards published in *IGCH* in 193 sections in 14 books.
- More than 1,400 coins in the ANS collection are referenced
- 139 Roman Imperial coin types in OCRE
- 4 Roman Republican coin types in CRRO

This LOD-oriented approach may serve as a model for other academic publishers. When one considers books to be data, a printed volume is *derivative* of an electronic work, but the ebook holds the greatest potential for dynamic interoperability between disparate information systems.

DIGITAL NUMISMATICS WITHIN THREE YEARS

By mid-2018, a large portion of the ANS' backlist will be made openly available on the web and integrated into the Society's other digital projects. The Society's archives and library materials comprise only a small percentage of all research materials related to Greek coins, but the cohesive research ecosystem combining Library, Archive, and Museum content stands as a major advancement of the research infrastructure in numismatics from a decade ago, and the potential will continue to grow as more organisations begin to adopt these technical methodologies.

In the near future, several advancements with respect to the coinage of Alexander and other Hellenistic dynasts may be expected as the Hellenistic Royal Coinages project moves toward completion. PELLA will be expanded to include all Antigonid kings. The second half of Seleucid Coins Online will be published by mid-2018, and Ptolemaic Coins Online will be ready for the public by 2020. *IGCH* will be transformed from a geographically tagged set of HTML descriptions into a robust database in the same vein as Kris Lockyear's Coin Hoards of the Roman Republic (<http://numismatics.org/chrr>)¹³. The remaining Newell notebooks will be annotated and linked to relevant coins, hoards, and other entities within the ANS's databases and external information systems. Importantly, an umbrella research site will be developed to combine all of the disparate Hellenistic datasets into one comprehensive platform, joining PELLA, Seleucid Coins, and Ptolemaic Coins Online together, opening the doors to new research questions.

The introduction of IIIF into this numismatic research ecosystem holds much promise. At present, the implementation of these APIs facilitates zoomable images in both MANTIS and online type corpora. In conjunction with the development of a definitive LOD-oriented index of all Greek monograms as part of the HRC project, image annotation of these monograms will make it possible to use IIIF's inherent APIs to extract only the annotated portion of an image. The URI for a monogram will show an idealised Screen Vector Graphics image that is infinitely scalable (and thus, printable), as well as its many variations that appear on physical objects extracted in real-time from Nomisma's IIIF collaborators. Much like hoards or types, where geographic distribution may be visualised with maps and timelines, the same monogram may appear on many different coin types, and these types may have been produced at different mints over a long duration. It will therefore be possible to map the circulation of the monograms themselves over time and space, and these visualisations may lead to new interpretations of their function and meaning within Greek monetary or social history. These expertly curated image annotation datasets may even provide a foundation for Machine Learning based on Computer Vision, enabling coin identification and die linking much more quickly and accurately than traditional methods.

In summation, this paper has provided an overview of the digital activities of the American Numismatic Society since 2010. Beginning with the collection itself and migrating into types and hoards, the recent endeavour of integrating library and archival materials into the numismatic research space has yielded positive results – the whole of this research

Library, Archive, and Museum ecosystem is greater than the sum of its parts. As a result, current and future generations of numismatists will be able to apply traditional research methods more quickly while enabling new sorts of research questions that could not have been asked of these datasets even ten years ago.

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